

Search strings executed:

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(("Barrett-Lennard Relationship Inventory"[All Fields]
OR Mehrabian Emotional Empathic Tendency Scale[All Fields]
OR "Toronto Empathy Questionnaire"[All Fields]
OR "Jefferson Scale of Physician Empathy"[All Fields]
OR Barrett-Lennard Empathy Scale[All Fields]
OR "Interpersonal Reactivity Index"[All Fields]
OR "Empathy Quotient"[All Fields]
OR "Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale"[All Fields]
OR "Multifaceted Empathy Test"[All Fields]
OR "Perth Empathy Scale"[All Fields]
OR Empathy Index for Children and Adolescents[All Fields]
OR "Basic Empathy Scale"[All Fields]
OR empath*[All Fields]
OR empathy[All Fields])
AND (innovat*[All Fields] OR enterprise[All Fields] OR entrepreneur*[All Fields]))
AND ("1900/01/01"[Date - Publication]: "2024/01/01"[Date - Publication])

Scopus

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